

**LEADERSHIP SERVICE ETIQUETTE AS THE MOST IMPORTANT PART OF
UNIVERSAL CULTURE**

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Annotation: *This article discusses the rules of etiquette and ethics, their importance in society and the main tasks of management in compliance with the rules of etiquette in the performance of their duties.*

Keywords: *society, leadership, etiquette, ethics, duties, duties and responsibilities, management etiquette, high culture.*

In practice, no official, diplomatic, political, economic, cultural or other relationship in society can take place without etiquette norms accepted and enforced by the international community. Interaction with governmental, non-governmental and non-profit organizations and other forms of the population, the public, guests from different walks of life has been strictly adhered to and improved by the rules of etiquette and ethics.

"We still live in a subjective situation," said President Islam Karimov. In our social life, the economy, the laws of life do not work in many places. Old-fashioned thinking, old-fashioned views, dependency still remain our main enemy, our weakest point.

The best way to get rid of these diseases is to raise young people to leadership positions who have got rid of the old stereotypes and are striving for innovation "[1].

During the years of independence, the requirements for leaders began to be radically reformed. Their clear roles, duties and responsibilities have been defined. In addition, compliance with the rules of etiquette of management in the performance of the duties of the leader is one of the main tasks. At the same time, the rise to a new level of compliance with the rules of service etiquette is not only a sign of the culture of civil servants, but also a sign of professional competence. In general, the conditions require the improvement of the subject, the personality of the leader, the priority of issues related to the characteristics of personnel in the field of management.

The way people interact with each other requires adherence to etiquette rules. The culture in which they interact with each other is called etiquette, and the rules of behavior are called etiquette rules.

The concept of etiquette is derived from the French word "etiquette", which in Russian means a label, and in Uzbek - a label [2]. The word label is now accepted in all languages. The concept of etiquette has its own history: King Louis XIV of France gives

guests a card with the words "rules of conduct" at one of the ceremonial receptions. The card is called a label. Over time, the word label has become a word of etiquette and the rules written in it have become etiquette rules and are still used today without changing its meaning. For example, in the Russian dictionary, etiquette is defined as a defined order and form of behavior in a society.

The rules of etiquette formed in society are called ethical norms. Ethical norms in society today have long been a positive result of human interaction. Obedience to these rules serves as a guarantee of interstate political, economic and cultural relations, because it is impossible to live in peace without respecting each other and maintaining the boundaries of behavior towards other states. In addition, adherence to the rules of etiquette serves as a guarantee of peaceful coexistence of people of different nationalities, different strata of our society and people with different worldviews who follow different religions in a market economy.

The rules of etiquette must be observed not only between states, but also by every member of society and members of professional groups. Everyone who considers himself civilized should not only know the basics of etiquette, but also obey them, because self-discipline and correct behavior in communication facilitates communication, provides an opportunity to understand each other faster, is a guarantee of stable communication.

The main requirement of modern etiquette is to ensure a harmonious inner and outer culture that encourages the individual to a higher culture, and requires a perfectly formed morality, both internally and externally.

Etiquette, which is an element of a person's external behavior, is based on the person's internal qualities. This implies that a person who follows the rules of etiquette must be distinguished by discipline and order. A disciplined person does not be rude to others, does not show "shows", does not offend other people with bad words.

Any person, especially a leader, has no right to sit in a leadership position if he does not gain the trust of the people with his labor, knowledge and experience, moral qualities, but, on the contrary, loses his prestige and dignity in their eyes [3].

Etiquette is formed primarily through behavior and customs. Etiquette norms cannot be considered in isolation from ethical principles.

Etiquette cannot enter into relationships with people by showing respect, which is the most important thing for people without a moral foundation. In terms of work ethic, the authors emphasize that etiquette is multifaceted. They emphasize once again the importance and infinity of the role of this industry in the management process.

It should be noted that everyone who is cultured and educated will never violate the established order in society by his words, actions and deeds, will not offend others and will not insult their honor. A civilized person obeys the rules of etiquette not only in formal ceremonies but also at home. Unfortunately, it is not uncommon for people

to disobey the rules of etiquette at home. They treat people differently and at home in a completely different way, for example, they are polite to other people, friends and subordinates, and at home they are rude and obscene. Their hypocritical behavior and demeanor are only a sign of their lack of culture.

Modern etiquette defines the rules of conduct and behavior of people in marriage, service, public places, on the street, hospitality and official events. That is why etiquette has been the notion of goodness, justice and humanity of all peoples for centuries and is the largest and most important part of human culture.

Professional etiquette is the rules of conduct and conduct of members of joint groups in the profession in relation to each other, between managers and their subordinates, as well as in relation to their professional duties. Therefore, the etiquette of professional groups consists of the rules of interaction of professionals working in the enterprise, the organization, managers and specialists of the enterprise with their subordinates, as well as the attitude of employees and specialists to the population and loyalty to their professional duties.

From the above, it can be concluded that in addition to the above, the rules of professional etiquette also include aesthetic requirements for professional work clothes, their appearance and speech. Meeting these aesthetic requirements is an indication of compliance with the rules of etiquette.

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